

Description of *Crisilla didyme* n. sp. from the Mediterranean Sea (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Rissoidae)

Descrizione de *Crisilla didyme* n. sp. del Mar Mediterraneo (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Rissoidae)

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ABSTRACT

A new Mediterranean species of the genus *Crisilla* Monterosato, 1917 (Rissooidea, Rissoidae) is described: *Crisilla didyme* n. sp. All known specimens come from the type locality: a submarine cave at Salina Island, Aeolian Islands, Southern Tyrrhenian Sea, Italy. It is compared with the most similar congeners from the Mediterranean Sea: *Crisilla beniamina* (Monterosato 1884), *C. aartseni* (Verduin 1984), *C. ramosorum* Oliver, Templado & Kersting, 2012, *C. maculata* (Monterosato, 1869) and from the Eastern Atlantic: *C. innominata* (Watson, 1897), *C. postrema* (Gofas, 1990) and *Crisilla* sp. (Romani *et al.*, 2018). *Alvania simulans* Locard, 1886 is also compared with the new species, and a potential relationship with *Crisilla* for this species is suggested.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie mediterránea del género *Crisilla* Monterosato, 1917 (Rissooidea, Rissoidae): *Crisilla didyme* n. sp. Todos los ejemplares conocidos provienen de la localidad tipo: una cueva submarina en Isla Salina, Islas Eolias, Mar Tirreno Meridional, Italia. Se compara con los congéneres más similares del mar Mediterráneo: *Crisilla beniamina* (Monterosato 1884), *C. aartseni* (Verduin 1984), *C. ramosorum* Oliver, Templado y Kersting, 2012, *C. maculata* (Monterosato, 1869) y del Atlántico oriental: *C. innominata* (Watson, 1897), *C. postrema* (Gofas, 1990) y *Crisilla* sp. (Romani *et al.*, 2018). *Alvania simulans* Locard, 1886 también se compara con la nueva especie, y se sugiere que esta posiblemente relacionada con *Crisilla*.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Crisilla* Monterosato, 1917 (type species *Turbo semistriatus* Montagu, 1808) was introduced for a: "group all consisting of semistriated forms, exquisite, blond, more or less vivid and with darker spots at the suture and the periphery" ["...gruppo tutto composto di forme semistriate, squisite, bionde, più o

meno vivide ed a macchiette più scure soturali e nella periferie..."] (Monterosato, 1917: 14). It has been considered as a subgenus of *Alvania* (e.g. PONDER, 1985; OLIVERIO, AMATI & NOFRONI, 1986; FASULO & GAGLINI, 1987), and then, raised as a distinct genus by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993),

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Table I. List of the Recent Mediterranean species of the genus *Crisilla*.
 Tabla I. Listado de las especies actuales del género *Crisilla* en el Mediterráneo.

Species	Figures
<i>Crisilla aartseni</i> (Verduin 1984)	Figure 2C
<i>Crisilla beniamina</i> (Monterosato 1884)	Figure 2A
<i>Crisilla chiarellii</i> (Cecalupo & Quadri 1995)	
<i>Crisilla gagliniae</i> (Amati, 1985)	
<i>Crisilla galvagni</i> (Aradas & Maggiore, 1844)	
<i>Crisilla maculata</i> (Monterosato, 1869)	Figures 2B-B1
<i>Crisilla marioni</i> (Fasulo & Gaglini 1987)	
<i>Crisilla ramosorum</i> Oliver, Templado & Kersting, 2012	Figure 2D
<i>Crisilla semistriata</i> (Montagu, 1808)	
' <i>Alvania</i> ' <i>simulans</i> Locard, 1886	Figures 2G-J
<i>Crisilla didyme</i> n. sp.	Figures 1A-K

based on the homogeneity of the shell features, and as such it is currently employed (e.g. SCAPERROTTA, BARTOLINI & BOGI, 2011; OLIVER, TEMPLADO & KERSTING, 2012; SCUDERI & AMATI, 2013; OLIVER, ROLÁN & TEMPLADO, 2019). Recently, the genera *Alvania* and *Crisilla* have proven as reciprocally non-monophyletic in a preliminary molecular phylogenetic analysis of the Rissoidae, yet *Crisilla beniamina* and *Crisilla galvagni* were undoubtedly very closely related to each other (CRISCIONE ET AL., 2016).

The species currently included in *Crisilla* form a rather homogeneous group of rissoids in shell morphology (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993), with features somehow intermediate to that of the genera *Alvania* Risso, 1826 and *Setia* H. Adams & A. Adams, 1852. There are some constant differences with species more comfortably allocated in *Setia*: the shell is generally larger and thicker, with at least a weak spiral sculpture and rarely also an axial one; additionally some species of *Crisilla* show a labial thickening (typically present in *Crisilla semistriata*), which is never present in *Setia*; finally, most *Crisilla* species generally live in deeper waters than those of *Setia*, down to the several hundred meters in the case of *Crisilla amphiglypha* Bouchet and Warén, 1993.

The rissoid genus *Crisilla* as currently conceived, comprises species of

small size for the family (c. 2.0 mm in height), with shell from scarcely to very robust, with weak spiral sculpture and rarely with weak axial sculpture. It includes 36 Recent recognised species in the northeastern Atlantic and in the western Indian Ocean (MOLLUSCABASE, 2018), of which 9 in the Mediterranean Sea (Table I): *Crisilla aartseni* (Verduin 1984), *C. beniamina* (Monterosato 1884), *C. chiarellii* (Cecalupo & Quadri 1995), *C. gagliniae* (Amati, 1985), *C. galvagni* (Aradas & Maggiore, 1844), *C. maculata* (Monterosato, 1869), *C. marioni* (Fasulo & Gaglini 1987), *C. ramosorum* Oliver, Templado & Kersting, 2012 and *C. semistriata* (Montagu, 1808). They live from the intertidal to upper continental shelf. All species, except three (*C. semistriata*, *C. transitoria* Gofas, 1999 and *C. monicae* Oliver, Rolán & Templado, 2019), have a paucispiral protoconch indicating non-planktotrophic development. The alpha-taxonomy of the genus *Crisilla* has been recently revised in the East Atlantic (e.g. VERDUIN, 1984; TEMPLADO & ROLÁN, 1994; OLIVER ET AL., 2019) and the Mediterranean Sea (e.g. FASULO & GAGLINI 1987; CECALUPO & QUADRI 1995; SCUDERI & AMATI, 2012).

'*Alvania*' *simulans* Locard, 1886 (Figs 2G-J) is not a typical *Alvania* in its shell features, but rather is similar in shell features to species of *Crisilla*, particularly to *C. beniamina* (Fig. 2A) and *C. galvagni*

(SCUDERI & AMATI, 2012) due to the presence of evident spiral cordlets on the whorls and the almost lack of axial sculpture. In some species of *Crisilla* the axial sculpture is more marked (e.g. *C. semistriata*, *C. transitoria*, *C. monicae*) or less marked (e.g. *C. javieri* Oliver, Rolán & Templado, 2019, *C. callosa* (Manzoni, 1868) and *C. marioni* Fasulo & Gaglioli, 1987). Furthermore, the texture and profile of the shell, the chromatic pattern and sculpture of the teleoconch are more similar to those of the *Crisilla* species. Therefore, we would not be surprised if future genetic studies will prove that '*A. simulans*' belongs in *Crisilla*.

We report here the description of a new species, found in a bioclastic sand sample, collected at Salina Island (Aeolian Archipelago) similar to *Crisilla ramosorum* Oliver, Templado & Kersting, 2010, but easily diagnosed by some shell features.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The samples here studied are stored in public and private collections, as detailed under each species (see abbreviations), and in the 'Type material' and 'Other material examined'. Photographs have been taken with a Sony Cyber-Shot digital camera mounted on a Kyowa KBS stereomicroscope, edited with the

Combine-Z software (Hadley, 2006). Most SEM photographs were taken with a Philips XL30 at the interdepartmental Laboratory of electron Microscopy (LIME: University "Roma Tre", Rome). Current systematics is based on the World Register of Marine Species (MolluscaBase, 2019).

Abbreviations and acronyms

BA: Bruno Amati collection (Rome, Italy);
CS-PM: Carlo Smriglio-Paolo Mariottini collection (Rome, Italy);
DO: Joan Daniel Oliver Baldoví collection (Madrid, Spain);
DS: Danilo Scuderi collection (Catania, Italy);
MCZR: Zoological Museum (Rome, Italy);
MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid, Spain);
MNHN: National Museum of Natural History (Paris, France);
MO: Marco Oliverio collection (Rome, Italy);
NHMW: Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (Wien, Austria);
SB-MS: Stefano Bartolini-Maria Scaperrotta collection (Florence, Italy);
SEM: scanning electron microscope;
sh: empty shell (s);
lv: live collected specimen (s) with soft parts.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795
Subclass CAENOGASTROPODA Cox, 1960
Superfamily RISSOIDEA Gray, 1847
Family RISSOIDAE Gray, 1847
Genus *Crisilla* Monterosato, 1917

Type-species: *Turbo semistriatus* MONTAGU, 1808: 136 (by monotypy)
= *Crisillosetia* F. NORDSIECK, 1972, Type species: *Setia (Crisillosetia) pseudocingulata* F. Nordsieck, 1972 (by original designation)

Crisilla didyme n. sp. (Figs. 1A-K, Table II)

Type material: holotype (MNHN-IM-2000-35035), H 1.45 mm, W 0.92 mm (Figs 1A-C); 2 paratypes (MNHN-IM-2000-35036); 2 paratypes (MCZR-M-00092/P); 2 paratypes (NHMW-MO-113278), 20 paratypes (BA), 20 paratypes (MO), 5 paratypes (CS-PM), 5 paratypes (DS). All from type locality.

Table II. Measurements of protoconch and teleoconch of *Crisilla didyme* n. sp., from a random sample of 15 adult specimens, in mm.

Tabla II. Medidas de la protoconcha y teleoconcha de *Crisilla didyme* n. sp., a partir de una muestra aleatoria de 15 especímenes adultos, en mm.

	holotype	paratype (Fig. 1H)	Min-Max
Protoconch	height	0.25	0.21-0.27
	diameter of nucleus	0.09	0.09-0.12
	diameter of first half whorl	0.17	0.17-0.22
	maximum diameter	0.32	0.27-0.35
	number of whorls	1.35	1.3-1.6
Teleoconch	height	1.45	1.40-1.65
	width	0.92	0.87-1.05
	height of aperture	0.68	0.60-0.70
	height/width ratio	1.576	1.430-1.666
	height/height aperture ratio	2.132	2.043-2.333
	number of whorls	2.3	2.3-3

Other material examined: 71 sh, (of which 14 broken) type locality (BA).

Type locality: Salina Island, Sicily, "Gamberetti" Cave, -35 m

Etymology: from the old Greek name of Salina Island (Αιδύμη, Didymē).

Distribution: so far known only from the type locality: Salina Island, Southern Tyrrhenian Sea, -35 m, only empty shells.

The bioclastic sediment sample was collected on the bottom of a shallow cave; c. 220 mollusc species were represented in the sample, almost 80% represented by empty shells, including also for the large part specimens from other biocoenoses, and a few (e.g. *Lucinoma spelaeum* Palazzi & Villari, 2001 e *Nucula perminima* Monterosato, 1875, two species quite common in this sample) considered as preferential of dark or semi-dark habitat (PALAZZI & VILLARI, 2001: 3).

Description (between parentheses data of the holotype): Shell (Figs 1A-K) small for the genus, not very solid, height 1.40-1.65 (1.45) mm, width 0.87-1.05 (0.92) mm, aperture height 0.60-0.70 (0.68) mm, height/width ratio 1.513-1.666 (1.576), height/aperture height ratio 2.071-2.333 (2.132), glossy, ovate-conic, with 2.3-3 (2.3) very convex whorls, suture impressed. Protoconch paucispiral (Figs 1I, K) of 1.3-1.6 (1.35)

whorls, height 0.21-0.27 (0.25) mm, diameter of the nucleus 0.09-0.12 (0.09) mm, diameter of the first half whorl 0.17-0.22 (0.17) mm, maximum diameter 0.27-0.35 (0.32) mm, sculptured with 4-5 fine, spaced, spiral cordlets of varying strength, often interrupted (Fig 1I) Protoconch-teleoconch boundary slightly marked, prosocline.

Teleoconch sculptured with rare and very fine spiral threads on the subsutural area of the last whorl, and weak prosocline growth lines (Fig 1J). Outer lip prosocline, simple, very weakly thickened, with sharp edge, internally smooth.

Colour: amber-yellow background, translucent, with two series of quadrangular blotches on the first whorls and above the aperture (9-12 (9) on last whorl), often longitudinally elongated, nearly fused; a third subsutural series, occasionally a fourth series around the umbilical area.

Operculum and soft part unknown.

Remarks: Recently, the genus *Crisilla* has been extensively revised (OLIVER ET AL., 2019). This revision focused on the

Figure 1. *Crisilla didyme* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 1.45 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-35035); D, E: paratype, 1.5 mm (BA); F, G: paratypes, 1.52 mm and 1.55 mm (BA); H-K: paratype, 1.45 mm (MCZR-M-00092/P) (all from the type locality).

Figura 1. *Crisilla didyme* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 1,45 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-35035); D, E: paratipo, 1,5 mm (BA); F, G: paratiposs, 1,52 mm y 1,55 mm (BA); H-K: paratipo, 1,45 mm (MCZR-M-00092/P) (todos de la localidad tipo).

species of Macaronesia (Azores, Madeira, Selvagens and Canary Islands), dividing the species into three groups, based on the shell morphology:

(1) species similar to *Alvania*, including taxa with weak spiral and axial sculphure and with a thick shell; (2) typical *Crisilla* species, including taxa with only

spiral sculpture, strong or weak; (3) species similar to *Setia*, including taxa with thin and small shell, lacking axial sculpture and with very weak or absent spiral sculpture. In this scheme, *Crisilla didyme* n. sp. should be included in the 'typical *Crisilla* species' group.

Crisilla beniamina (Monterosato, 1884) (MONTEROSATO, 1884: 228; see also SCAPERROTTA ET AL., 2011: 70, 5 unnumbered figures; APPOLLONI ET AL., 2018: 103, figs K, L; ROMANI ET AL., 2018: 15, figs 8 E-H; OLIVER ET AL., 2019: 27, 74, figs 1 E, F, 30 D) (Fig 2A) differs from *C. didyme* n. sp. for its protoconch sculpture of granules over the whole surface grouped in series of spiral cordlets, more marked towards the end of the protoconch, with one cordlet in the adapical quarter generally more evident, its larger sizes (up to 2 mm in height v. 1.65 mm in *C. didyme* n. sp.), the evident spiral sculpture on the teleoconch, more marked in the periphery, the umbilical chink present v. absent in *C. didyme* n. sp. *Crisilla beniamina* extends almost throughout the Mediterranean Sea. It has been found sympatric with *C. didyme* n. sp.

Crisilla aartseni (Verduin, 1984) (VERDUIN, 1984: 74, fig. 8; see also GOFAS & OLIVER, 2011: 190, 3 unnumbered figures; OLIVER ET AL., 2012: 61, figs 28-29; SCAPERROTTA ET AL., 2015: 63, 6 unnumbered figures; OLIVER ET AL., 2019: 27, figs 1 K, L) (Fig 2C) differs from *C. didyme* n. sp. for its protoconch sculpture of a dozen fine but strong, tightly packed spiral cordlets, the slight subsutural depression and the lack of spiral sculpture on the teleoconch. *Crisilla aartseni* is only known on the southern coast of Portugal and in the Strait of Gibraltar.

Crisilla ramosorum Oliver, Templado & Kersting, 2012, (OLIVER ET AL., 2012: 61, figs 23-27; see also OLIVER ET AL., 2019: 27, figs 1 I, J) (Fig 2D) differs from *C. didyme* n. sp. in its lower protoconch 0.18 mm v. 0.21-0.27 in *C. didyme* n. sp., sculptured by broader 4-6 spiral cordlets, some interrupted; in its smaller average size (height 1.20-1.30 mm v. 1.40-1.65 mm in *C. didyme* n. sp.), the

angled periphery v. not angled or barely so in *C. didyme* n. sp., in the teleoconch spiral sculpture, more marked on the base v. absent in *C. didyme* n. sp. *Crisilla ramosorum* is limited to eastern Spain.

Crisilla maculata (Monterosato, 1869) (MONTEROSATO, 1869: 7, fig. 1, see also VERDUIN, 1984: 74, fig. 7; SCAPERROTTA ET AL., 2015: 77, 5 unnumbered figures; APPOLLONI ET AL., 2018: 105, figs L, M; OLIVER ET AL., 2019: 27, fig. 1A) (Fig 2B) differs from *C. didyme* n. sp. for its protoconch sculpture of granules arranged in about 10-12 spirals, the nucleus of the protoconch dark (Fig 2B1) v. of the same colour as the rest of the shell in *C. didyme* n. sp., the larger size (exceeding 2 mm v. 1.65 in *C. didyme* n. sp.), the spire less cyrtocoid with slightly convex whorls, v. whorls more convex in *C. didyme* n. sp., one or two weak spiral cords occasionally present on the base v. absent in *C. didyme* n. sp.; its larger height/width ratio (1.696-1.822 v. 1.513-1.666 in *C. didyme* n. sp.). *Crisilla maculata* lives in most of the Mediterranean Sea, particularly in the central sector. It has been found sympatric with *C. didyme* n. sp.

Crisilla innominata (Watson, 1897) (WATSON, 1897: 309, pl. 19, 20; see also VERDUIN, 1988: 26, figs 29; OLIVER ET AL., 2019: 55, 73, figs 18 A-G, figs 19 A-J, 29 H, I) (Fig 2E) differs from *C. didyme* n. sp. for its protoconch sculpture of granules, arranged in spiral series, more or less welded together, its spiral sculpture on the teleoconch always present (often more delicate or absent in the median part of the whorls), its more robust shell. *C. innominata* ranges in the Macaronesia (Madeira and Canary Islands) in the Atlantic Ocean (OLIVER ET AL., 2019).

Crisilla postrema (Gofas, 1990) (GOFAS, 1990: 114-116, figs 8, 24-27, see also ÁVILA ET AL., 2002: 364, fig. 75; FRIAS MARTINS ET AL., 2009: 139, figs 120-122; OLIVER ET AL., 2019: 57, 73, figs 20 A-G, 29 J) (Fig 2F) is very similar to *C. didyme* n. sp. for having a weak teleoconch spiral sculpture, more marked on the base; it differs from *C. didyme* n. sp. for its protoconch sculpture of confused

Figure 2. *Crisilla* spp. A: *Crisilla beniamina* (Monterosato 1884), Salina Is., 1.95 mm (BA); B: *Crisilla maculata* (Monterosato, 1869), Filicudi Is., 1.73 mm (SB-MS), (B1: protoconch); C: *Crisilla aartseni* (Verduin, 1984), Tarifa, 1.3 mm (SB-MS); D: *Crisilla ramosorum* Oliver, Templado & Kersting, 2012, holotype, Columbretes Islands, 1.2 mm (MNCN.15.05/60050); E: *Crisilla innominata* (Watson, 1897), Canary Islands, Gran Canaria, Gando, 1.4 mm (DO); F: *Crisilla postrema* (Gofas, 1990), Azores, Terceira, Biscoitos, 1.4 mm (DO); G, H – I, J: ‘*Alvania*’ *simulans* (Locard, 1886), Marettimo Is. (1.47 mm and 1.4 mm, respectively) (MO).

Figura 2. *Crisilla* spp. A: *Crisilla beniamina* (Monterosato 1884), isla Salina, 1,95 mm (BA); B: *Crisilla maculata* (Monterosato, 1869), isla Filicudi, 1,73 mm (SB-MS), (B1: protoconcha); C: *Crisilla aartseni* (Verduin, 1984), Tarifa, 1,3 mm (SB-MS); D: *Crisilla ramosorum* Oliver, Templado & Kersting, 2012, holotipo, islas Columbretes, 1,2 mm (MNCN.15.05/60050); E: *Crisilla innominata* (Watson, 1897), islas Canarias, Gran Canaria, Gando, 1,4 mm (DO); F: *Crisilla postrema* (Gofas, 1990), Azores, Terceira, Biscoitos, 1,4 mm (DO); G-J: ‘*Alvania*’ *simulans* (Locard, 1886), isla Marettimo (1,47 mm y 1,4 mm, respectivamente) (MO).

and irregular spiral cordlets, some interrupted, others welded together, its weak umbilical chink (absent in *C. didyme* n. sp.). *Crisilla postrema* is supposedly endemic to the Azores, although HOENSELAAR & GOUD (1998) reported two shells from Madeira (OLIVER ET AL., 2019).

Some specimens ascribed to an undetermined *Crisilla* sp. from Lastovo Island (Croatia), have been briefly described and excellently figured by ROMANI ET AL. (2018: 15, fig 8C). These specimens closely resemble the new

species, as well as *C. ramosorum* and *C. aartseni*. However, they are diagnosed by the presence of a weak basal cord (absent in *C. didyme* n. sp.), and the more numerous spots on the last whorl (c. 16 according to the photo, v. 9-12 in *C. didyme* n. sp.), suggesting they may represent a further undescribed species.

'*Alvania*' *simulans* Locard, 1886 differs in its more slender profile, the protoconch with more numerous (c. 12) spiral cordlets, the teleoconch with strong spiral sculpture and evident microsculpture.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- APPOLONI M., SMRIGLIO C., AMATI B., LUGLIÈ L., NOFRONI I., TRINGALI L. P., MARIOTTINI P. & OLIVERIO M. 2018. Catalogue of the primary types of marine molluscan taxa described by Tommaso Allery Di Maria, Marquis of Monterosato, deposited in the Museo Civico di Zoologia, Roma. *Zootaxa*, 4477 (1): 001–138 [Monograph].
- ÁVILA S.P., AMEN R., AZEVEDO J.M.N., CACHÃO M. & GARCÍA-TALAVERA F. 2002. Checklist of the Pleistocene marine molluscs of Prainha and Lagoinhas (Santa Maria Island, Azores). *Açoreana*, 9 (4): 343–370.
- BOUCHET P. & WARÉN A. 1993. Revision of the Northeast Atlantic bathyal and abyssal Mesogastropoda. *Bollettino Malacologico*, Supplement 3: 579–840.
- CRISCIONE F., PONDER W.F., KOHLER F., TAKANO T. & KANO A. Y. 2016. Molecular phylogeny of Rissoidae (Caenogastropoda: Rissooidea) allows testing the diagnostic utility of morphological traits. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 179 (1): 23–40.
- FRIAS MARTINS A.M., BORGES J.P., ÁVILA S.P., COSTA A.C., MADEIRA P. & MORTON B. 2009. Illustrated checklist of the infralittoral molluscs off Vila Franca do Campo. *Açoreana*, Supplement 6: 15–103.
- GOFAS S. 1990. The littoral Rissoidae and Anabathridae of São Miguel, Azores. *Açoreana*, Supplement: 97–134.
- GOFAS S. & OLIVER J.D. 2011. Familia Rissoidae. In GOFAS S., MORENO D. & SALAS C. (Eds): *Moluscos marinos de Andalucía. Vol. 1*. Servicio de Publicaciones e Intercambio Científico, Universidad de Málaga: 167–194.
- GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI R., PUSATERI F., PALMERI A. & EBREO C. 2002. *Atlante delle conchiglie marine del Mediterraneo, vol. 2 (Caenogastropoda parte 1: Discopoda-Heteropoda)*. Edizioni Evolver, (Prima Ristampa e corretta) 258 pp.
- HADLEY A. 2006. Combine ZP public domain image processing software. Available from <https://web.archive.org/web/20160221032141/http://www.hadleyweb.pwp.blueyonder.co.uk/>

- HOENSELAAR H.J. & GOUD J. 1998. The Rissoidae of the CANCAP expeditions, I: the genus *Alvania* Risso, 1826 (Gastropoda Prosobranchia). *Basteria*, 62: 69-115, 1998
- LOCARD A. 1886. *Prodrome de malacologie française. Catalogue général des mollusques vivants de France. Mollusque marins*. Lyon, H. Georg & Paris, Baillièrè : pp. X + 778.
- MONTAGU G. 1808. *Supplement to Testacea Britannica*. White, London. 184 pp., pls. 17-30.
- MONTEROSATO T.A. (DI) 1869. *Testacci nuovi dei mari di Sicilia*, I. Mirto, printed for the Author, Palermo, 18 pp.; 1 pl.
- MONTEROSATO T.A. (DI) 1884. Conchiglie littorali mediterranee. *Il Naturalista Siciliano*, 3 (8): 227-231.
- MONTEROSATO T.A. (DI) 1917. Molluschi viventi e quaternari raccolti lungo le coste della Tripolitania dall'Ing. Camillo Crema. *Bollettino Zoologico Italiano*, Ser. 3, 4: 1-28, pl. 1 (fig. 1-35).
- MOLLUSCABASE, 2019. *Alvania simulans* Locard, 1886. Accessed at: <http://www.molluscabase.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=141238> on 2019-07-06.
- MOLLUSCABASE, 2019. *Crisilla* Monterosato, 1917. Accessed at: <http://www.molluscabase.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=138446> on 2019-07-06.
- OLIVER J.D., ROLÁN E. & TEMPLADO J. 2019. The littoral species of the genus *Crisilla* Monterosato, 1917 (Caenogastropoda, Rissoidae) in Azores, Madeira, Selvagens and Canary Islands with notes on West African taxa and the description of four new species. *Iberus*, 37 (1): 23-80.
- OLIVER J.D., TEMPLADO J. & KERSTING D. 2012. Marine gastropods of the Columbretes Islands (Western Mediterranean). *Iberus*, 30 (2): 49-87.
- OLIVERIO M., AMATI B. & NOFRONI I. 1986. Proposta di adeguamento sistematico dei Rissoidae (sensu Ponder) del mar Mediterraneo. Parte I: famiglia Rissoidae Gray, 1847 (Gastropoda: Prosobranchia). *Notiziario del C.I.S.Ma.*, 7-8: 35-52 [1985/1986].
- PALAZZI S. & VILLARI A. 2001. Molluschi e Brachiopodi delle grotte sottomarine del Taorminese. *La Conchiglia*, 297 (suppl.): 56 pp.
- PONDER W.F. 1985. A review of the Genera of the Rissoidae (Mollusca: Mesogastropoda: Rissoacea). *Records of the Australian Museum*, Supplement 4: 1-221.
- ROMANI R., RAVEGGI A., SCAPERROTTA M. & BARTOLINI S. 2018. Contributo alla conoscenza della malacofauna marina delle isole adriatiche. 1. Nota sui micromolluschi marini conchiferi rinvenuti sulla costa settentrionale dell'isola di Lastovo [Lagosta] (Croazia, Mar Adriatico Sud-Orientale). *Alleryana*, 36 (1): 1-22.
- SCAPERROTTA M., BARTOLINI S. & BOGI C. 2011. *Accrescimenti. Stadi di accrescimento dei molluschi marini del Mediterraneo. Volume V. L'Informatore Piceno*, Ancona, 184 pp.
- SCAPERROTTA M., BARTOLINI S. & BOGI C. 2015. *Accrescimenti. Stadi di accrescimento dei molluschi marini del Mediterraneo. Volume VII. L'Informatore Piceno*, Ancona, 192 pp.
- SCUDERI D. & AMATI B. 2012. Rediscovery and re-evaluation of a "ghost" taxon: the case of *Rissoa galvagni* Aradas et Maggiore, 1844 (Caenogastropoda Rissoidae). *Biodiversity Journal*, 3 (4): 511-520.
- VERDUIN A. 1984. On the taxonomy of some recent European marine species of the genus *Cingula* s. l. *Basteria*, 48: 37-87.
- VERDUIN A. 1988. On the taxonomy of some Rissocean species from Europe, Madeira and the Canary Islands. *Basteria*, 52: 9-35.
- WATSON R.B. 1897. On the marine Mollusca of Madeira; with descriptions of thirty-five new species, and an index-list of all the known seawdwelling species of that island. *Journal of the Linnean Society of London, Zoology*, 26: 233-329, pls. 19-20.

